

Free Will Manifesto

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Ignacio Ospino Ms C. Information Science

Independent Researcher, Florida, USA

<https://orcid.org/0009-0009-0831-9810>

Email: ignacio.ospino@gmail.com

Telephone +1 561 7167334

In the free will discussion, incompatibilism is, in my opinion, the correct position when formulated as follows:

If strict determinism is true, there cannot be human free will.

On the other hand, I have determined that I have free will. My free will empowers me to do so and, in so doing, I fulfill my free will. This is not a vicious circle or a circular argument; it is a virtuous loop. In such a loop, the output of the system is fed back into the input, creating a self-sustained dynamic behavior.

My will is, of course, less free if I do not believe in free will. Those who believe strict determinism to be true will argue that my realization of free will was pre-determined by the universe since the Big Bang and is therefore not free. According to them, the fact that it was predetermined takes freedom from my will because I had no other choice than to realize that I have free will, or to believe so. My reaction to that argument is to thank them for letting me know that my free will was unavoidable and to tell them that this in no way makes me feel less free. Others may say that what I believe to be free will is just an illusion. Well, as one of my heroes said about time: "It is a very persistent one."

To those who attempt to negate my free will based on scientific arguments and the assumption of strict determinism, I say: You are free to believe that you have no free will. But that does not make me less free. Exercising your free will or not is their free will decision. If they use their free will to negate free will, so be it. There is no restriction on their free will stopping them from doing so,

and that is precisely why it is free. However, I am also free to believe that they have free will, and they have simply chosen to use it to deny free will. I must respect their free will to do so. If they claim to know that I have no free will and that I merely pretend to have one, they are just using their free will to analyze mine and attempt to negate it. That is where I say: "Sorry, sir, you are free to believe you have no free will, but you cannot stop me from having free will and believing in it." The deniers and ignorers are also free; they, too, are using their free will as they please.

I firmly state that I have a will (do not dare to negate that), and my obligation as a rational being, is to logically and rigorously determine how and to what extent my will is free. I need to understand it correctly. If I do not correctly comprehend the nature and limitations of my free will, I may fail to exercise it and perhaps conclude that I do not have one.

The most popular position in this discussion is to assume strict determinism as the true understanding of the world and then consequently negate the possibility of free will. Others argue that determinism and free will are "compatible" or that free will has nothing to do with determinism or indeterminism or that, what we believe to be free will is an emergent island in an infinite deterministic ocean. But very few dare to examine the validity of the deterministic belief with $p=1$ as defined below. If science, as some understand it, were a church, its chief dogma would be determinism. And no one wants to be excommunicated for even considering a revision of determinism. That is the problem.

Some scientists believe that there is a universal wave (function) that is deterministic. They believed that if you know the exact description of that wave today, you can reconstruct its history at any past moment and uniquely predict its future evolution with probability $p=1$, leaving no room for probabilistic distributions of the outcomes. That, in my opinion, is a rigorous definition of the belief in determinism. However, there is a problem: an exact description of a continuous wave requires infinite information. Therefore, all descriptions or models of the wave rely on approximations and simplifications in the mathematical representation, so the premise is unobtainable, as well as the aspiration of having only one possible future for each present. Those models are epistemically useful, but is it rigorous to make them equal to ontic reality? Can a perfect picture be considered to be the same as the object it portrays? We don't think so.

Everything and everyone ride a sub-wave of the universal wave, which is also believed to be deterministic. We are riding an inherited horse, but we and the horse have become by assumption the same entity. Every wave is supposed to perfectly describe reality in informational

terms, without any uncertainties, as every well-behaved deterministic wave should. But is such a wave equal to reality? No, it is an idealization, a useful model but not an exact duplication of reality. We insist: The assumption of wave continuity in space-time necessitates infinite information for an exact description. However, infinite information is impossible to achieve because it implies infinite energy, which is not possible in a finite universe. This is why, when we measure the wave, we do not obtain deterministic values but discrete and probabilistically determined ones.

The discrepancy between assuming a continuous and deterministic wave and obtaining discrete, probabilistic results upon measurement is called the "Measurement Problem." This problem remains unsolvable, even when the solution seems obvious to me: recognizing probabilistic determinism—the idea that if we knew the exact description of the wave function today, we could reconstruct its history at any past moment, because all past probabilistic outcomes are now known with $p=1$, but its future evolution follows probabilistic distributions rather than absolute certainty. The probabilities for future outcomes are still $0 < p < 1$ and we cannot be certain about the outcomes. It is my understanding that this probabilistic understanding reflects the behavior of the universe.

The unitarity principle in quantum theory is often used to defend determinism. It states that the sum of all probabilities for the states of a system remains 1 over time, meaning the total information in an isolated quantum system does not change. However, the principle is derived under the assumption of a time-invariant Hamiltonian and system isolation. In such a system, entropy does not grow, and determinism holds. But even if unitarity is derived by other means, it contradicts the objective growth of ontic information in and for the universe as dictated by the Second Law of Thermodynamics.

When I last checked my wave, it was evolving in time and interacting with the environment. Therefore, I am not an isolated deterministic system in the quantum mechanical sense. Macro systems like the Earth, cities, or human beings cannot be regarded as deterministic. They become probabilistic when correctly considered as non-isolated systems in a discrete space where time flows, and the ontic entropy of the universe grows. Classical mechanics and relativity model such systems with differential equations, leading some to assume determinism. But this is incorrect: differential calculus is an approximation, and it assumes continuous space-time, which I and others

rightfully dispute. Even if we accept space-time continuity, an exact description will then require infinite information, rendering strict determinism implausible.

Most systems influencing human life—climate, economics, pandemics—are chaotic, unstable, or at best probabilistic-deterministic. We use information and energy to introduce predictability into our lives, but certainty is never absolute, as $p=1$ probabilities are an artificial construction, an approximation, not a feature of nature.

To those who insist that I lack free will, I explain: Life is unpredictable. The best we can anticipate are probabilities. Some probabilities are extremely high, and we approximate them to 1. I assume that the sun will rise tomorrow, but the probability for that is still less than 1. Being a conscious being, I use information to estimate probabilities of events affecting my survival or well-being. Because I have free will, I can choose to influence and bias these probabilities according to my interests. If I believe a certain political outcome will harm society, I attempt to alter its probability. We are not powerless. We influence events probabilistically, and our success is proportional to the energy and information we invest in the effort.

I ride my wave. It may seem deterministic, but sometimes I decide to dismount because I judge it beneficial. When I do, I choose left or right, guided by my subjective interest. This is how I break the deterministic illusion—by making probabilistically determined choices that matter. And, it could not be otherwise, the outcomes of my efforts are also probabilistically determined. No outcome is granted but I always hope my choices enhance human survival and my well-being with a reasonable probability. That is my free will.

For those who remain on their deterministic horses, believing everything is preordained with $p=1$, I wish them luck. As for me, I have chosen to understand, exercise, and nurture my free will.

And if this means excommunication from the "church of strict determinism," so be it—I never belonged in the first place.